

Habitat connectivity workflow to support decisions and trade-offs between local stakeholders

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Summary

Habitat connectivity is a crucial biodiversity metric that illustrates human-induced challenges to ecosystems. To provide stakeholders with a decision-making tool for trade-offs related to land-use/land-cover (LULC) transformations, a workflow to compute terrestrial habitat connectivity was devised for the area of Catalonia (Spain), involving: (1) analysis of multi-sensor remote sensing imagery, (2) obtaining open-access spatial data on connectivity barriers, (3) LULC mapping, (4) content-analysis of connectivity studies, (5) computing connectivity using open-source Graphab software based on graph theory, (6) forecasting connectivity to reveal potential biodiversity loss triggered by LULC changes and (7) tools deployment through Docker containers and HPC mode.

KEYWORDS: biodiversity, connectivity, GIS, land-use/land-cover (LULC), decision-making.

1 Introduction

Habitat connectivity is now a crucial biodiversity metric that illustrates human-induced challenges to ecosystems (Keeley et al., 2021). The biodiversity topic stands as a fundamental milestone in global and European policy strategies. For instance, the EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030 advocates for the "creation... of ecological corridors as part of a Trans European Nature Network to prevent genetic isolation, allowing for species migration and the maintenance and enhancement of healthy ecosystems."

The objective of this study is to develop a novel tool for assessing the terrestrial landscape connectivity of habitats by integrating well-established software, open-access and user-defined spatial data. This aims to facilitate trade-offs among stakeholders, fostering win-win situations, particularly in the context of proposed or planned land-use/land-cover (LULC) changes.

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2 Computation workflow

A detailed workflow to compute connectivity and provide users with the insights on the consequences of LULC changes has been devised, as follows:

1. LULC mapping from multi-sensor remote sensing imagery
2. Refinement of raster data
3. Content-analysis of connectivity studies
4. Computing connectivity through Graphab software
5. Post-processing connectivity
6. Forecasting connectivity
7. Optimisation and deployment of connectivity computation tool

2.1 LULC mapping from multi-sensor remote sensing imagery

LULC map series (1987-2017) of Catalonia (MUCSC) have been created by CREAM, UAB and the Generalitat de Catalunya (Gonzalez-Guerrero and Pons, 2020) through the automatic classification of Landsat and Sentinel-2 images. To mitigate edge effects in the connectivity calculation and cover habitats surrounding Catalonia (Figure 1), the MUCSC has been combined with three ancillary LULC maps:

- The CORINE land cover map (France) (Spanish National Geographic Institute, 2017).
- The Land Cover Map of Andorra (The Institute of Andorran Studies, 2012).
- The Spanish SIOSE Map (Aragón and València).

2.2 Refinement of raster data

Due to the limited resolution of the satellite imagery, the LULC classification described in 2.1 is not capable of detecting all connectivity barriers, including human-made (roads and railways) and natural ones (waterways and water bodies). As an illustration, small streams are not consistently represented, as they may be separated due to drying or overshadowing by tree canopies (Figure 2). Hence, a nested workflow to refine and enrich raster data with vector data on linear barriers was implemented (Figure 3). An adverse "edge effect" by which infrastructure reduces the suitability of nearby habitats for plants or animals was also considered.

To consider all connectivity barriers and avoid any gaps, the OpenStreetMap portal (2024) was accessed to gather reliable vector data, produced by the public and aligned with Citizen Science principles.

Figure 1: Transregional issue of connectivity - polygons of LULC types are intersecting various protected areas within Catalonia, neighbouring regions and countries (LULC types are shown in colour for Catalonia only)

Figure 2: Waterways derived from OSM as compared to their representation on MUCSC maps

Figure 3: Nested workflow for refining LULC maps

The Nominatim API (2023) was tested to retrieve vector data from OpenStreetMap (OSM) across the case study area, providing a swift solution to import vector data for Catalonia ¹. The results of the nested workflow are stored as single temporary geopackage files for further processing (Figure 4).

2.3 Content-analysis of habitat connectivity studies

It is necessary to define the concrete characteristics of species and habitats in order to compute functional habitat connectivity which is relevant to those organisms and landscapes - average or maximum dispersal distance, minimum patch area, ecological parameters of optimum habitat, and habitat suitability. Small mammals that are particularly well-studied may be considered target species for computations in Catalonia (e.g., *Martes martes*, *Mustela nivalis*, *Suncus etruscus*, etc.).

2.4 Graphab computations

Amongst the tools for habitat connectivity computations, Graphab - based on graph theory - (Foltête et al., 2021) is one of the most powerful open-access software packages for estimating indices at various scales. It can be run either from a GUI or in command-line mode to optimise batch computations². A few widely known connectivity indices (Saura and Pascual-Hortal, 2007; Estrada and Bodin, 2008) were chosen for implementation into connectivity computations at this stage:

- BC (Betweenness Centrality Index).
- IIC (Integral Index of Connectivity).
- PC (Probability of Connectivity).

2.5 Post-processing connectivity

Technical steps to ingest computation outputs to access, use and visualise data are:

- Translation of output GeoTIFF files into Cloud Optimised Geotiff with LZW compression and format transformations to avoid Float64 and Int64, if possible.
- Joining txt and csv files with index values in each habitat patch to the TIFF files containing unique identifiers (ID) of patches.
- Merging outputs into multi-band GeoTIFF files, containing all output indices and patch IDs.

These steps may be extended if netCDF4 format is considered to be better performed to access data by end user through OGC APIs.

¹Github. <https://github.com/AD4GD/pilot-2/tree/main/preprocessing>

²Github. <https://github.com/AD4GD/pilot-2/tree/main/graphab>

Figure 4: Detailed workflow of retrieving and preprocessing OSM data

2.6 Connectivity forecasting

Any significant LULC changes may be assessed through semi-automatic computation to reveal the potential transformation in connectivity. This helps decision-makers to understand how LULC transformations (e.g. wetland drainage, or, conversely, the design of ecosystem corridors) may impact connectivity between separated habitats.

The Graphab tool called "landmod" was used to enable upload of user-defined vector data on planned LULC changes and update connectivity indices. As an illustration, the hypothetical construction of a new road near the Natural Park de Collserola could result in a decline in IIC (Figure 5) for *Martes martes*, which primarily inhabits dense woodlands. The IIC of small new patch is estimated to be 0.00058 compared to the IIC of non-separated patch before LULC changes = 0.02858.

Figure 5: Connectivity indices of woodland habitats: above - before road construction, below - after road construction

2.7 Optimisation and deployment of tool

Connectivity indices require a significant amount of time to compute due to the complexity of graph design. Therefore, the Graphab application and input data were deployed on a high-performance computing (HPC) platform via a Docker container, its configuration file, and image.

An initial draft of the front-end tool with options to upload data (input LULC data and examples of vector connectivity maps) has been published as a webpage based on Leaflet.

Currently, two Graphab's and one Miramon's outputs are available through restricted access on the FAIRiCUBE³ virtual machine in test mode to perform spatial queries from a raster data cube.

³FAIRiCUBE. <https://fairicube.rasdaman.com/>

3 Discussion

The limitations to applying this workflow stem mainly from OSM data, which requires the additional preprocessing:

- Text values assigned with keys that are supposed to be numerical only ('width').
- An Abundance of null values, particularly within 'width' and 'level' columns.
- Inconsistency in assigning values for specific keys (for instance, an overlap between 'intermittent' and 'seasonal' keys concerning waterways) due to the discrepancy between user opinions and extending the set of keys as OSM develops (Figure 6).

Figure 6: Differences in specifying 'intermittent' (a) and 'seasonal' (b) keys for Catalonian waterways

OSM data in relatively urbanized areas of Europe are widely known to be reliable (Zhou et al., 2022), relative to the spatial resolution of input LULC raster data. However, it is recommended to use authoritative data on barriers (e.g. from governmental institutions or topography surveys) in areas remote from settlements rather than OSM.

Considerable further improvements are planned to the connectivity computation tool:

- Optimising Graphab code through distribution and spawning procedures using the native MPI mode to reduce computation time.
- Customising preprocessing step to upload flexible vector data relevant to other study areas.
- Design of user-friendly front-end application for semi-automatic computations.

4 Conclusion

The workflow devised is capable of providing information to stakeholders such as researchers, the public (including members of Citizen Science projects), government institutions (especially transport

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